

Exploring the transport-health-environment nexus through a new ‘Health Rating Index’ for Dublin, Ireland

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Summary

This paper examines the spatial distribution of accessibility to health benefits and exposure to health risks at the small area level in Dublin, Ireland for four key factors: primary healthcare services, green space, air quality, and road noise. The primary goal is to combine granular spatial data on these environmental health benefits and risks into a composite open source ‘Health Rating Index’ (HRI), and then compare it to urban sociodemographic, built environment, and transport features.

KEYWORDS: social and environmental determinants of health, air pollution, transport geography, health indices, spatial machine learning

1. Introduction

There is now an established recognition in health research that social and environmental factors play a significant role in supporting individual and population health (Giles-Corti and Donovan, 2002; Gordon-Larsen et al. 2006; Braveman et al. 2010; Prüss-Ustün et al., 2017). Specifically, better spatial access to health services lowers health system costs and improves a variety of health outcomes, especially for deprived population groups (Shi et al. 2005; Starfield et al. 2005; Saxon and Snow, 2020). Urban green space provides a variety of important benefits to cities, including removing atmospheric pollutants (Nowak et al. 2006) and providing positive mental and physical health benefits to residents (Callaghan et al. 2020; Kabisch et al. 2021). At the same time, prolonged exposure to both air and noise pollution can cause a variety of negative health outcomes, including asthma, lung cancer, and cardiovascular disease (among others) (WHO, 2022; Hanigan et al. 2019).

Given the inherently spatial nature of these effects (and the resulting pattern of population health outcomes), there has been a growing interest in quantifying social and environmental determinants of health in spatial data through multi-dimensional indices (Illiev and Cheshire, 2024). This paper examines the spatial distribution of accessibility to health benefits and exposure to health risks at the small area level (65-90 households) in Dublin, Ireland for four key factors: primary healthcare services, green space, air quality, and road noise. The primary goal is to combine granular spatial data on these environmental health benefits and risks into a composite ‘Health Rating Index’ (HRI) and then compare the distribution of the HRI to various urban characteristics to better understand the role that sociodemographic, built environment, and transport features play in shaping the structural ‘healthiness’ of neighbourhoods in Dublin.

2. Methods and data

Figure 1 shows a diagram of the methodology for calculating the composite Health Rating Index (HRI), including specific equations for each ‘benefit’ and ‘risk’ component.

We started by calculating spatial accessibility to health ‘benefits’ (primary healthcare and green space). To operationalise access to primary healthcare, we used the two-step floating catchment area (2SFCA) method to calculate the accessibility of each small area centroid (k) to General Practitioner (GP)

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locations (j) (taken from [Ireland's Open Data Portal](#)) within 15-minute walking isochrones calculated along Dublin's pedestrian street network (Luo and Wang, 2003; Ghomrawi et al. 2024).

Next, we used two approaches for defining access to green space, both originating from OpenStreetMap (OSM) data. For the first, we calculated a measure of “gravity”-based accessibility ($greens_i$) from each small area centroid (i) to the nearest 10 randomly-generated points within each OSM green space polygon (j), discounted by a specific logistic decay function g used in previous work to accurately reflect walking distance accessibility (Credit et al. 2024). The second green space accessibility metric we used is the mean ‘green index’ value for each small area taken from the *greenR* R package, which provides a measure of OSM green space accessibility along individual *street network* segments (Mahajan, 2024). We turned these street network segments into chained points spaced every 5m and averaged the green index values for these points within each small area ($greenr_i$).

Health Rating Index (HRI)

Figure 1 Diagram showing the specific methods for calculating each of the individual elements of the Health Rating Index (HRI), including health ‘benefits’ and ‘risks’.

For the health ‘risks’ (air quality and road noise), we calculated estimates of premature mortality for both exposure to air pollution and road noise. For air pollution, the data come from the 2021 Google/Dublin City Council (DCC) [Air View Dublin](#) project, which involved equipping Street View cars with air quality sensors to capture average concentrations of various harmful pollutants, including PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and O₃, along street network segments. We used this data – by averaging the concentration of chained points within each small area[†] – to estimate the excess risk of premature death from all causes due to air pollution ($PDair$) based on the WHO’s updated health risk assessment methodology (Annex 1, 2022).

For road noise, DCC conducted a noise exposure study in 2011, with the requisite data published on the [Dublinked](#) open data portal, which we used to estimate the excess risk of premature death from ischemic heart disease (IHD) due to road noise ($PDnoise$) based on the methodology of Hanigan et al. (2019). While the general structure of the methodology is similar to that used for air pollution, it is

[†] Excluding points within a 5m buffer of the Dublin Port Tunnel, which runs underground.

adjusted slightly to provide a small area-specific population-weighted mortality rate.

To combine these features into a single measure, the final estimates of PD_{air} and PD_{noise} were first added together for each small area, which is possible since these figures are provided in the same units (i.e., excess deaths). This total was then divided by the population of each small area and reported in terms of total estimated premature deaths per 100,000 population (PD_{env}). Each of the final environmental health benefits and risks were then combined into a composite weighted index; since there is no strong *a priori* reasoning for a particular weighting scheme, a naïve equally-weighted split between benefits (GP , $greenr$, and $greens$) and risks (PD_{env}) is used[‡], as shown in Equation 1:

$$HRI_i = \left(\frac{1}{4}\right) GP_i + \left(\frac{1}{8}\right) greenr_i + \left(\frac{1}{8}\right) greens_i - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) PD_{env_i} \quad (1)$$

The HRI is then used as the dependent variable in a random forest (RF) model using the *ranger* R package trained on a random 70% sample of the data with a number of relevant sociodemographic, transportation, and spatial covariates, including (from the 2022 Census) % Bachelor’s degree attainment or higher, % commuting by non-auto modes, % reporting ‘bad’ or ‘very bad’ health, and population density, along with their spatial lags (calculated using a queen contiguity spatial weights matrix). The natural log of distance to the nearest primary or secondary road, the spatial lag of HRI, and dummy variables for each Dublin postcode and all small areas south of the river Liffey (a historical socioeconomic dividing line) are also included in the model. The RF model was chosen over a standard linear model due to its ability to capture complex, nonlinear associations between features. In this case, the RF also outperformed an identically-specified XGBoost model in terms of root mean squared error (RMSE): 0.633[§] for RF compared to 0.637 for XGBoost.

3. Results

Figure 2 shows the permutation importances for the independent variables from the RF model, as well as accumulated local effect (ALE) plots - which visualise the overall ‘accumulation’ of the local effects of a given covariate on the predicted value of y (from the model) – for the independent variables of interest (Apley and Zhu, 2020; Apley, 2022). Figure 3 shows individual maps of the five layers that make up the composite HRI – green space accessibility, green index, and GP accessibility on the ‘benefit’ side, and PD_{air} and PD_{noise} on the ‘risk’ side – as well as the final composite map of HRI.

Taken together, these results indicate that transport, social, and built environment factors are important for structuring access to environmental health benefits and risks. First, the pattern of the HRI is very spatially-clustered, with distinct spatial “hotspots” in the affluent portions of the city, including south Dublin (south of the Liffey) and west of Phoenix Park (e.g., Castleknock). Distance to primary and secondary roads is the second-highest predictor of HRI, which is likely because the environmental health risks assessed here – air pollution and road noise – are tightly related to higher concentrations of auto traffic, as shown in Figure 4 D-E. While this relationship is unsurprising, the high importance demonstrated by the model underscores the critical role that transportation infrastructure plays in environmental health outcomes. Educational attainment, population density, and non-auto commuting are also all positively – and non-linearly – related to HRI.

[‡] An alternative weighting scheme (1/3 for benefits and 2/3 for risks) was also tested with this model specification but provided worse accuracy (0.825 for random forest and 0.830 for XGBoost).

[§] Based on a range of HRI values from -9.97 (min) to 1.49 (max).

Figure 2 Permutation importances and selected accumulated local effects (ALE) plots from the random forest model for predicting Health Rating Index (HRI) by small area.

HRI is also a reasonably good predictor (9th most-important) of self-reported health when tested in a similar RF model (with HRI as the independent variable of interest). As shown in Figure 3, the percent of people per small area reporting ‘bad’ or ‘very bad’ health decreases consistently with HRI, with a significant difference in poor health between small areas with HRI < -1 (the lowest ~3% of observations) and all others.

Figure 3 Accumulated local effects (ALE) plot showing the relationship between Health Rating Index (HRI) (as an independent variable) and % of people reporting ‘bad’ or ‘very bad’ health (as dependent variable) by small area.

Figure 4 Maps of the five layers that make up the composite Health Rating Index (HRI) – A) green space accessibility, B) green index, C) GP accessibility, D) estimated premature deaths from road noise, E) estimated premature deaths from air pollution – and F) the final composite map of HRI. Basemap data from OpenStreetMap (OSM).

4. Conclusions

While sociodemographic factors certainly play a role in the distribution of health risks and benefits in the city, this paper's results also speak to the important (and often overlooked) role that transport planning and urban form have on health outcomes. HRI is higher in neighbourhoods with higher densities, higher rates of non-auto commuting, and higher distances from larger, high traffic volume roads. These findings are particularly important for understanding the substantial (and direct) health implications of auto-oriented transport planning, which continues to be a primary focus for investment in the Irish transportation system. In the future, to improve health outcomes, this analysis framework could be used to test alternative planning scenarios, e.g., the impact on mortality from reduced air pollution and noise due to construction of an underground metro system, or the increased accessibility from locating additional green spaces and GPs in particular neighbourhoods.

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Biographies

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